

Pre-service English teachers' motivation to pursue a career in teaching viewed from speaking self-efficacy

Hartono Hartono¹, Nani Hidayati¹, Wiyaka Wiyaka²

¹English Education Department, Faculty of Languages and Communication Sciences, Universitas Islam Sultan Agung, Semarang, Indonesia

²English Education Department, Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, Universitas PGRI Semarang, Semarang, Indonesia

Article Info

Article history:

Received Nov 29, 2021

Revised Sep 3, 2022

Accepted Sep 22, 2022

Keywords:

Career in teaching

Career motivation

English teacher

Pre-service English teacher

Speaking self-efficacy

ABSTRACT

Previous research on pre-service teachers' motivation to pursue a career in teaching found different results. Some research found altruistic motivation dominant in determining career decisions, while others suggest extrinsic or intrinsic motivation. The current study extended the topic by relating pre-service English teachers' motivation to teach to English-speaking self-efficacy. There were 94 pre-service English teachers of different semesters participated in this study. Data were collected with a Likert-type questionnaire. Pre-service English teachers have a high motivation to pursue a career in teaching, and extrinsic motivation was the most dominant motive. The nobility of the profession, sustainability of job demand, inspiration from the teachers, and flexible working hours are among the extrinsic motives. The pre-service teachers also have a high level of English-speaking self-efficacy. However, they still have problems with anxiety, the use of idioms, the use of accurate grammar and vocabulary, and fluency. Between motivation to teach and their speaking self-efficacy lies a significant positive correlation at a moderate level. This moderate level of the relationship suggests that English-speaking self-efficacy is not a determining factor in motivating pre-service English teachers to have a career in teaching. Consequently, some English teachers may have inadequate proficiency in the language they teach.

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Corresponding Author:

Hartono Hartono

English Education Department, Faculty of Languages and Communication Sciences,
Universitas Islam Sultan Agung (UNISSULA)

Raya Kaligawe street, Km. 4 Semarang, Central Java, Indonesia

Email: hartono@unissula.ac.id

1. INTRODUCTION

Several previous research on pre-service teacher career choices focuses on the role of motivational influences [1]–[3]. There were three types of motivation identified, namely intrinsic, extrinsic, and altruistic motivation. Intrinsic motive is something from within as interest, personal experience, and intellectual fulfillment. It is when an individual has an instinctive passion for teaching and genuinely enjoys it. On the other side, the extrinsic motive is something from the outside job of teaching itself, such as working hours, salary, holidays, the economic condition of service, and social status. Finally, an altruistic motive is an individual's desire and intention to contribute to the growth of another individual. In this case, teaching is seen as a socially worthwhile and important job [4]–[6].

Previous research on pre-service teachers' motivation to pursue a career in teaching found different results. The study of Azman [7] involving 425 first-year undergraduate student teachers who had just started

their pre-service teacher training program found that altruistic and extrinsic factors were dominant motives in deciding a teaching career for male and female students. The motivation to contribute to society and to help the government achieve its vision and the perception that teaching is a respected job and a service of moral value, as well as loving children, are among the altruistic motivations that encourage students to make a career in teaching. While job security, job compatibility with parenthood, an opportunity for further study, and workload are extrinsic motives.

According to Topkaya and Uztosun [5], after surveying 207 first and fourth-grade pre-service teachers of an English Language Teaching Department of a faculty of education in Turkey (81.6% were female and only 18.4% were male) using factors influencing teaching choice (FIT-Choice) scale found that pre-service teachers, in general, were more intrinsically motivated. However, altruistic motives such as shaping child and adolescent values, influencing the next generation, providing service to society, and making social contributions were mostly rated highly. Another study by Balyer and Ozcan [8] involving a bigger number of respondents (1,410 student teachers of Education Departments from different public universities) with data collected through a scale called choosing teaching profession as a career scale (CTPCS) found that the altruistic-intrinsic motivation was the most dominant motivation for female students to choose a teaching career. On the other hand, male students, especially those from poor and crowded families, had extrinsic motivation. Motivation to help others, enjoyment of being together with children, enjoyment of working in a school environment, and personality fit were among the reasons encouraging students to choose a teaching career.

In the Indonesian context, a study investigated the motivations of education students to pursue careers in teaching. A FIT-choice model was used. The study found that motivations for choosing teacher education fall into four: social utility values, prior teaching and learning experience, intrinsic career values, and interestingly, religious values. Social utility values such as making a social contribution, enjoying working with children/adolescents, and enhancing social equity were rated highly. Intrinsic value was also rated highly. It was even higher than personal utility [9].

In addition to investigating the pre-service teachers' motivational factors, the current study extended the topic to students' self-efficacy, specifically their English-speaking self-efficacy. Three research objectives were proposed: i) to analyze the Indonesian pre-service English teachers' motivation to pursue a career in teaching; ii) to analyze the pre-service teachers' speaking self-efficacy; and iii) to find a possible relationship between the motivation to teach and the English-speaking self-efficacy.

Previous studies showed that self-efficacy relates to career choices and decisions. It is a major variable facilitating career development [10], [11]. Deciding what career to choose requires a lot of consideration because a career choice will affect an individual's life physically and mentally. The individual's perception of his ability to accomplish tasks set out in a particular career or profession determines how an individual will approach it, whether he will choose the profession or not. Teaching task demand, expertise, difficulties, and individual perceived ability to teach affect motivation to pursue the career. Students perceived self-efficacy influences professional aspirations [12], and self-efficacy contributes to people's career decision-making [13]. Other studies [14]–[16], all confirmed that there is a correlation between self-efficacy and career choice and aspiration. However, studies focusing on English-speaking efficacy are still very limited. In the South Asian context, it was found that English teachers' self-efficacy beliefs and language proficiency intersect to shape teaching behavior [17].

Today, researching English-speaking self-efficacy and teaching motivation of Indonesian pre-service English teachers is relevant. First, in the context of English language learning and teaching, teachers play an essential role as language models for their students [18]; therefore, they must be proficient in the language they teach. This proficiency is a necessary condition for effective language teaching [19]. Teachers must demonstrate to their students how English is used either during instructions or outside the classroom. This role is crucial as, among other ways, students learn by observing and imitating their teachers, and in many parts of Indonesia, classrooms still become one of the important places where students can be exposed to English [20]. The language that teachers speak and use serves as a language input which becomes a prerequisite for acquisition [21]. This role should be emphasized as English teaching in Indonesia has not been very successful [22], [23], as indicated by the low proficiency of Indonesian learners after years of learning English [24], [25]. Another studies found that one of the causing factors is the low proficiency of the teachers [20], [26]–[28].

Secondly, the right and high motivation to teach is indispensable. Teachers are expected to excel and play a significant role in providing students with a high-quality education [29]. Teachers' role in preparing future generations is central, therefore, having highly motivated, qualified, and dedicated individuals in the teaching profession is crucial [8]. Teachers' motivation determines the success and performance of the educational system and is one of the most significant contributors to optimizing teachers' performance [30]. In addition, knowledge, background experiences, motivation, and beliefs teachers bring to the classroom

influence the roles they play as teachers [4]. Studies show that students placed with high-performing teachers can progress three times as fast as those placed with low-performing teachers [31]. Teachers' motivation and commitment are crucial in the context of teaching English in Indonesia, which is a foreign language [23]. Innovations in teaching such as teaching strategies and methods, material development, and learning assessments can only be conducted by individuals with high motivation and commitment. Good teachers are those who can motivate students to get involved in learning through different types of methods or strategies.

Self-efficacy is people's beliefs about their ability to perform and manage tasks at hand successfully. It is people's judgment about their capabilities to exercise control over events that affect their life [32]. English-speaking self-efficacy in this study is an extension of the self-efficacy construct, which refers to students' judgment of their ability to perform English-speaking tasks. Self-efficacy is not a general state of judgment; instead, it is specific to a particular context and domain [33], [34]. In educational contexts, self-efficacy deals with students' beliefs about their academic capabilities. It predicts academic achievement and performance. The higher the efficacy is, the better students will perform [35], [36].

The construct of self-efficacy is derived from the Social Cognitive Theory of Bandura which suggests a model of causation involving the person, behavior, and environment in triadic reciprocally. What people think affects their actions, and these actions can change the environment. The environment, in turn, can change people's thoughts [37]. Students may expend a higher effort to learn (behavioral variable), if they feel competent in the subject they learn (self-efficacy as a personal variable). The teacher may praise them (social/environmental variable), which may substantiate their learning progress (personal variable). This, in turn, motivates the students to learn harder. People's self-efficacy is developed by four sources, namely mastery experience, which refers to the persons' experience in doing the tasks in question; a vicarious experience which is the experience of seeing other people doing the task; social persuasion in the forms of verbal support and encouragement of people around; and the last one is physiological and affective states which refer to individuals' physical and mental or emotional conditions when required to perform tasks.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Research design and respondents

This study adopted a quantitative research design. Data collected were numerical and analyzed quantitatively [38]. Statistics were used to describe and explain phenomena of interest, in this case, the pre-service English teachers' motivation to pursue a career in teaching and their English-speaking self-efficacy. The respondents of the study were the students of semesters 3, 5, and 7 of an English education study program at a university in Semarang, Central Java, Indonesia. The total population was 150 students. Students of semester 1 were excluded under consideration that, when the data were being collected, they had just started their study. By applying quota sampling, the study targeted to involve at least 50% of the total population (75 students) as the samples for the study. Until the date the data collection was scheduled to close, 94 students had participated. There were 42 students in semester 3 (44.68%), 26 students in semester 5 (27.66%), and 26 students in semester 7 (27.66). Based on gender, 13 of them were male (13.8%), and 81 were female (86.2%).

2.2. Instruments

Data were collected by questionnaires of three sections. The first section collected information on the semester the respondent was in and gender. This section also included optional forms to write the name and the student ID number, but most respondents had left the forms blank. The second section was to collect information about their motivation to pursue a career in teaching. This part of the questionnaire adopted a Likert-type model. There were 17 statements requiring responses from respondents on their level of agreement of strongly disagree, disagree, undecided, agree, and strongly agree. The statements measured three types of motivation, namely altruistic motivation (5 statements), intrinsic motivation (6 statements), and extrinsic motivation (6 statements).

The third section collected information about the respondents' English-speaking self-efficacy. It adopted the model suggested by Bandura of 'can do' statements [39], [40]. There were 18 statements of tasks and abilities related to English speaking. Respondents were asked to score their performance in a range of 0 to 100. A score of 0 indicates that they were utterly unable to perform the task, while a score of 100 indicates that they could perform the task perfectly. Bandura suggests that the strength of a self-efficacy questionnaire lies in its specificity in measuring specific skills [35], [41]. Therefore, designing a questionnaire with specific predictors of ability is very necessary. The statements in the questionnaire were developed based on the abilities involved in speaking English commonly faced and experienced by the respondents. Item validity of these questionnaires was measured by Pearson correlation. The correlation analysis found that all values of the items were higher than .207 ($n=94$). The Cronbach's alpha of the reliability test for the first questionnaire was .883, and for the second one was .978. These proved that the questionnaires were both valid and reliable.

2.3. Procedure

The researcher invited students to participate in the study by sending them a request and a link to a google form containing the questionnaire through the class WhatsApp group (WAG). Those who agreed to participate would open the link, fill in the questionnaire, and submit it. The responses of agreement levels on the questionnaire on career motivation were transformed into scores of 1 to 5. Strongly Disagree response was scored 1, Disagree was scored 2, and scores 3, 4, and 5 were consecutively for Undecided, Agree, and Strongly Agree. The item scores of the self-efficacy questionnaire were summed up for the total scores.

2.4. Data analysis

Firstly, the data were analyzed descriptively to find the minimum, maximum, and mean scores. This was to decide the level of both the motivation to teach and the English-speaking self-efficacy. Then, respondents were grouped into five categories very low, low, moderate, high, and very high. Secondly, scores of the motivation to teach and speaking-self efficacy were correlated to see whether a correlation between these two constructs existed.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Motivation to pursue a career in teaching

The first research objective to be addressed is the level of the pre-service English teachers' motivation to pursue a career in teaching. With 94 respondents, the descriptive statistical analysis resulted in the minimum score=53.00, the maximum score=85.00, the mean score=68.60, and the deviation standard=7.18. With 17 statements in which the lowest score possible is 1 and the highest score possible is 5, and 5 categories of motivation (very low, low, moderate, high, and very high), the mean score (68.60) indicates that the pre-service English teachers had a high level of motivation to pursue a career in teaching. Further analysis based on the motivation types (altruistic, intrinsic, and extrinsic) is presented in Table 1.

Extrinsic motivation has the highest mean score, followed by intrinsic and altruistic motivation. This means that extrinsic motivation is the most dominant factor in motivating Indonesian pre-service English teachers to pursue a career in teaching. Extrinsic motive is something from the outside of the job of teaching itself [4]–[6]. In this study, the motive was measured by the income that the English teachers may have, the nobility of the profession, the sustainability of job demand, the flexible working hours, and the inspirations brought by their teachers.

Table 1. Motivation by the types

Motivation	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev.
Altruistic	94	14.00	25.00	20.40	2.22
Intrinsic	94	14.00	30.00	22.34	3.67
Extrinsic	94	19.00	30.00	25.85	2.14
Valid N (listwise)	94				

The finding is different from the study of Azman, which found altruistic-extrinsic motivation the dominant factor in motivating pre-service teachers to pursue a career in teaching [7]. Azman suggested that factors motivating pre-service English teachers to pursue careers in teaching were the interplay between altruistic and extrinsic factors. It is worth noting, however, the subjects of Azman's study were pre-service teachers of different study programs, one of them was Teaching English as a Second Language (TESL), while the subjects of this study were pre-service teachers of only one study program, namely English Language Education which trains students to work as English teachers. The finding supports the study of Bastick [42], which found that extrinsic motivation was a dominating factor encouraging students to take the teaching profession in developing countries, but it is different from other studies [5], [9] which suggests that social utility and intrinsic values be the most important career motivation and the most dominating factor encouraging pre-service English teachers to pursue a career in teaching.

The data in Table 2 further describes the motivation by presenting the score of each statement in the questionnaire. The mean score of "teacher is a noble profession" (extrinsic) is the highest. Suryani, Watt, and Richardson argued that the nobility of the teaching profession in the Indonesian context is caused by religious values as most Indonesians are religious, and most religions in Indonesia view teaching as a noble profession [9]. The statement "the teaching profession is always required by society" (extrinsic) has the second-highest. This describes an employment prospect, explaining why students chose teacher education programs [43]. Though currently there seems to be an oversupply of teachers [44], they still believe that finding a teaching job was still relatively easier than finding a job in another profession. "My English teachers have inspired me

to be an English teacher” (extrinsic) highlights the model performed by English teachers. “Flexible working hours” (extrinsic) was also rated highly. This working hour was considered an advantage. Pre-service teachers may expect to share their time for other jobs, either teaching-related jobs such as running private courses at home or non-teaching jobs such as running some businesses and the like.

The statement “becoming an English teacher has been my ambition since I was a young child” (intrinsic) has the lowest mean score. It may suggest that for most Indonesians, future careers were not introduced, therefore were not developed at young ages. In addition, it may also confirm research finding [45] which concluded that half of the Indonesian undergraduate students were facing problems in deciding what jobs to have. Formally, a career is introduced when students are in senior high school as they prepare to continue their studies at universities. They are introduced to study programs at universities and possible careers they may pursue as they graduate.

The statement ranked the second-lowest is “I master English well, so I’m good to be an English teacher” (intrinsic). This may suggest that English-speaking competence is not a determining factor for choosing a teaching career. Besides becoming an English teacher, a graduate of an English education program may pursue a non-teaching career as becoming an interpreter, a translator, or working in business sectors where English language skill is required. Though not well-documented in research papers, many graduates who are good at English seem to be more interested in working in non-teaching sectors, for example, working in media industries or multinational companies as they may earn a more attractive salary. Having a good income was also rated low by the respondents. Perhaps, they have been fully aware that becoming teachers in this country will not give them a good salary. Studies show that teachers’ welfare correlates to teaching motivation. Low income may lead to low welfare and, finally, low motivation to teach. Since motivation affects performance, low income may put the quality of education at risk [46].

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of motivation indicators

Statement	N	Min	Max	Mean	Type	Rank
Being an English teacher is an interesting profession because I can help others learn.	94	2.00	5.00	4.13	A	7
Becoming an English teacher has been my ambition since I was a young child.	94	1.00	5.00	3.11	I	16
I can help students reach their dream.	94	3.00	5.00	4.31	A	5
Working as an English teacher is always easy and fun.	94	2.00	5.00	3.97	I	8
Becoming an English teacher will give me a good income.	94	1.00	5.00	3.64	E	13
I’m happy to work with young children.	94	3.00	5.00	4.52	A	3
By becoming an English teacher, I can always develop my English skills.	94	2.00	5.00	4.26	I	6
Teaching English is an easy job.	94	2.00	5.00	3.70	I	12
Teaching is a noble profession.	94	3.00	5.00	4.89	E	1
I mastered English well, so I’m good to be an English teacher.	94	2.00	5.00	3.56	I	15
The teaching profession is always required by society.	94	3.00	5.00	4.61	E	2
My English teachers have inspired me to be an English teacher.	94	2.00	5.00	4.52	E	3
I enjoy working at school.	94	2.00	5.00	3.84	E	10
A teacher has flexible working hours.	94	3.00	5.00	4.34	E	4
I love teaching.	94	2.00	5.00	3.57	A	14
I can help young people find good jobs.	94	2.00	5.00	3.85	A	9
Becoming an English teacher matches the academic program I am taking.	94	1.00	5.00	3.74	I	11
Valid N (listwise)	94					

A: altruistic, I: intrinsic, E: extrinsic

3.2. Pre-service English teachers’ speaking self-efficacy

The second research objective deals with the English-speaking self-efficacy of Indonesian pre-service English teachers. With 18 statements of 0 as the lowest score and 100 as the highest one, the minimum score achieved was 490, the maximum score was 1,650, the mean score was 1,250, and the deviation standard was 228.07. If speaking efficacy is grouped into five categories very low, low, moderate, high, and very high, this means the score belongs to the high level. This suggests that the pre-service English teachers in this study had a high level of English-speaking self-efficacy (the mean score was between 1,051 and 1,350). They had a strong belief that they could do various tasks involved in English speaking.

Table 3 presents respondents’ grouping into the levels of self-efficacy category. Most respondents (75.5%) belong to the high level, 10.6% have the moderate level, 9.6% have the very high, and 4.3% have a low level of English-speaking efficacy. No respondent stays at a very low level. If the number of respondents having high and very high was summed up, the number reaches 85.1%. As self-efficacy predicts performance, we can expect Indonesian pre-service English teachers have good English-speaking skills.

Table 3. Frequencies of self-efficacy category

	Levels	Freq.	%	Cum. %
Valid	Low	4	4.3	4.3
	Moderate	10	10.6	14.9
	High	71	75.5	90.4
	Very high	9	9.6	100.0
	Total	94	100.0	

The finding of this study is similar to the study of Darmawan, Alam, and Nirma [47], which investigated the speaking self-efficacy of pre-service English teachers enrolling in a speaking advanced class. As many as 79% of the respondents had a high level of English-speaking self-efficacy. The finding, however, is slightly different from the study of Alawiyah [48], which found that the majority of pre-service English teachers (59.37%) had a moderate level of speaking self-efficacy, 40.63% had high self-efficacy, and no one belonged to low self-efficacy. There were differences between this current study and previous study [48]. While, the research by Alawiyah [48] used only three levels of categories, this current study used five levels. The instrument was also different. The self-efficacy was measured by 28 items of indicators with responses on five scales of agreement from strongly disagree (SD) to strongly agree (SA) previously used by Asakereh and Dehghannezhad [49], referring to previous studies [39], [40]. This current study measured speaking self-efficacy with a score of 0 (zero) to 100. Table 4 shows the scores of self-efficacy indicators.

Table 4. Scores of self-efficacy indicators

Statement	N	Min	Max	Mean	Rank
I can pronounce English words and phrases fluently and correctly.	94	10.00	100.00	71.91	6
I can use nouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs, and other types of words in my speaking correctly.	94	20.00	100.00	74.25	1
I can speak English using correct and appropriate grammar.	94	10.00	100.00	64.78	14
When I speak, I can choose and use words and phrases correctly and meaningfully.	94	20.00	90.00	68.51	11
When I speak, I can use English idioms correctly.	94	20.00	90.00	64.25	16
When I speak, I can use English collocations accurately and appropriately.	94	20.00	100.00	70.00	9
I can make English sentences correctly.	94	30.00	100.00	71.48	7
I can always initiate English conversations with different people.	94	30.00	100.00	72.44	5
I can express my ideas and thoughts in English fluently.	94	30.00	90.00	64.68	15
I can explain things in English well.	94	30.00	100.00	67.76	12
I can ask questions in English well.	94	30.00	100.00	73.40	4
I can answer or respond to questions or statements in English well.	94	30.00	100.00	69.78	10
I can make different types of presentations in English well.	94	30.00	100.00	71.48	7
I can speak in English in front of many people without being nervous.	94	10.00	100.00	59.68	17
I can comment in English.	94	30.00	100.00	66.38	13
I can ask or command someone to do something in English appropriately.	94	30.00	100.00	71.17	8
I can make English conversations well.	94	30.00	100.00	73.61	3
I can do different types of speaking tasks assigned by my teachers well.	94	30.00	100.00	73.82	2
Valid N (listwise)	94				

The minimum, maximum, and mean scores of each indicator presented in Table 4 confirm that the respondents had high English-speaking self-efficacy. There were 17 out of 18 statements that resulted in mean scores above 61 and below 80. It is the range of a high level of self-efficacy. Only one indicator resulted in 59.68 of the moderate level. The five highest mean scores are statements "I can use nouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs and other types of words in my speaking correctly" (74.25), "I can do different types of speaking tasks assigned by my teachers well" (73.82), "I can make English conversations well" (73.61), "I can ask questions in English well" (73.40), and "I can always initiate English conversations with different people" (72.44). While the five lowest mean scores, which can be interpreted as a low belief in their ability, are "I can speak in English in front of many people without being nervous" (59.68), "When I speak, I can use English idioms correctly" (64.25), "I can express my ideas and thoughts in English fluently" (64.68), "I can speak English in correct and appropriate grammar" (64.78), and "I can comment in English" (66.38). Anxiety, subjective feeling of tension, apprehension, nervousness, and worry which very often arouses automatically from the nervous system [50], is still a major problem for pre-service teachers in improving their language skills as it has the lowest mean score indicating the lowest level of self-efficacy. This is in line with many previous research findings. Language learners experience a high level of anxiety when speaking in the target language [51].

3.3. Relationship between self-efficacy and motivation to teach

The third objective of the study was to find out whether there was a relationship between the pre-service teachers' motivation to pursue a career in teaching and their speaking self-efficacy. This research objective was motivated by the social cognitive career theory, which suggests the role of self-efficacy in career choices [52]. An individual's belief in his ability to perform tasks helps determine what career he may choose. It is hypothesized, knowing that much of the English teaching job involves English speaking, students' English-speaking self-efficacy will determine whether or not they take the job of teaching. For that purpose, scores of the motivation to teach (MT) and the speaking self-efficacy (SE) were correlated. Table 5 presents the result.

Table 5. Correlation between MT and SE

		Speaking self-efficacy	Motivation to teach
Speaking self-efficacy	Pearson Correlation	1	.389**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	94	94
Motivation to teach	Pearson Correlation	.389**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	94	94

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The table shows that the value of the correlation coefficient is $r=.389$, $p<.000$. Therefore, it is concluded that the Indonesian pre-service English teachers' motivation to teach was moderately correlated to their speaking self-efficacy. The positive coefficient value signs that the relationship is aligned [38]. If self-efficacy increases, so do the motivation to pursue a career in teaching. Accordingly, if self-efficacy is low, the motivation to teach is too. The value of sig. (2-tailed) ($p<.005$) further indicates that the relationship is significant. Although it is only at a moderate level, the correlation can still explain that speaking self-efficacy predicts students' decisions in taking teaching careers. People's judgment of their ability to accomplish a task will determine whether they will approach the task or not. This further supports that self-efficacy influences career choices and decisions [10], [11]. This is the behavioral consequence of self-efficacy [27], [49]. Self-efficacy drives employability and is positively affected by career aspiration [53], [54]. Self-efficacy is a determinant of career aspirations [15].

The moderate level of the relationship, however, suggests that English speaking skills are not determining factors for pre-service English teachers to pursue a career in teaching. Students taking an English Education program may not be motivated by the desire to be English teachers, but by the desire to learn and be proficient in English. They may expect to have jobs in businesses or industries. For some of them, teaching can be just a fallback career, a non-choice, or a last resort when a more desirable career option cannot be attained [55]. With good English proficiency, they may target more lucrative non-teaching careers such as working in media industries or multinational companies that can offer better income and facilities. Only when failing to achieve this, may they consider a teaching job. In addition, it also may mean that the data on motivation to pursue a career in teaching presented previously shows that good mastery of English was not a strong motivating factor for having a career in teaching. This may mean that these pre-service English teachers did not consider language proficiency as an important attribute of being an English teacher. As a result, many schools may not have qualified and proficient English teachers who can serve as language models for their students' language development. The study of Lie, Tamah, and Trianawatyrianawaty [56] proved this phenomenon. Novice teachers, teachers with teaching experience of fewer than five years, and apprentice teachers, with teaching experience between 5 to 10 years, still show inadequate English language proficiency. This low English proficiency may become one of the sources making English teaching in Indonesian schools not very successful [22], [23]. Teacher quality impacts students' learning outcomes [57]. Making students speak English fluently and proficiently requires motivated, fluent, and proficient English teachers working with them.

4. CONCLUSION

The study was motivated to address the topic of career choice of pre-service English teachers and their English-speaking self-efficacy. Three research objectives were put forward: analyzing the Indonesian pre-service teachers' motivation to teach, their English-speaking self-efficacy, and the possible correlation between those variables. The study found that Indonesian pre-service English teachers have a high motivation to teach and extrinsic motivation is the most dominant motive. Among the reasons are the nobility

of the teaching profession and the profession's sustainability as societies will always need teachers. Income is found not to be a strong motive to teach.

Besides having a strong motivation to pursue a career in teaching, Indonesian pre-service English teachers have a high level of English-speaking self-efficacy. Their belief in the ability to perform tasks in speaking is high. Since self-efficacy can predict performance, we expect that they can speak English well, although speaking anxiety, idiom usages, grammar, and fluency are still problems. The motivation to teach positively correlates to English-speaking self-efficacy at a moderate level. This indicates that English-speaking self-efficacy is not a dominating factor that encourages pre-service English teachers to pursue a career in teaching. Although this study does not show a causal relationship, we can still learn that maintaining a high level of self-efficacy is necessary to attract potential teachers to have careers in teaching as they graduate. As pre-service English teachers still have high anxiety and face problems related to idioms, appropriate grammar, and speaking fluency, English study programs, and their lecturers must design learning activities to address the issues. A possible cause-and-effect relationship between motivation to teach and self-efficacy can be a topic for further research.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The study was funded by the Research and Community Service Center of Universitas Islam Sultan Agung (UNISSULA). The researchers would like to thank the Rector of UNISSULA and the center for all the support in completing the research.

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BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Hartono is a lecturer at English Education Department of Universitas Islam Sultan Agung (UNISSULA). He got his Bachelor's degree from English Literature of Universitas Diponegoro and his Master's in English Education from Universitas Negeri Semarang. Currently, he is taking his Doctoral degree in language education at Universitas Negeri Semarang. His research interest is in second language acquisition, English language teaching, and career. He has published his research in journals, presented in conferences, and written books and modules. He can be contacted at email: hartono@unissula.ac.id.

Nani Hidayati is a lecturer at the English Education Department of Universitas Islam Sultan Agung (UNISSULA). She got her Bachelor's degree from Universitas Jenderal Sudirman in English Teacher Education and a Master's degree in English Education from Universitas Negeri Semarang. Her research interest is in teaching language skills such as speaking and writing and vocabulary. She has published articles in journals and proceedings. She can be contacted at email: nani@unissula.ac.id.

Wiyaka is a senior lecturer at the English Department Universitas PGRI Semarang. He holds a doctorate's degree (Dr.) in Language Education from Universitas Negeri Semarang (State University of Semarang), Indonesia. Besides teaching, he has worked with several research projects funded by the ministry of higher education and other sponsors. His interests in teaching and research include language assessment, reading, and writing. He has published research articles in several journals and authored textbooks in assessments. He can be contacted at email: wiyaka@upgris.ac.id.